

Discipline-specific terminology in an indigenous language of South Africa as panacea to the inaccessibility of academic spaces: Perspectives from isiZulu L1 students

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Discipline-specific terminology in an indigenous language widens English-oriented academic spaces in accessing knowledge and enhancing academic success for indigenous speakers. The University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN), South Africa, has embarked on the development of terminologies in isiZulu in twenty disciplines to date addressing the lack of academic vocabulary in indigenous languages. Using multilingualism and ‘language as a resource’ orientation to language planning as conceptual frameworks and through analysis of interview data, this paper explores the perspectives of isiZulu L1 students at UKZN on the use of terminology in isiZulu to determine whether these students acknowledge this terminology, and the extent to which they find this terminology resourceful. Findings indicate that these students appreciate the terminologies in isiZulu and find these helpful when studying. It is concluded that African languages are viable for use in academia and terminology in indigenous languages is one panacea to the inaccessibility of academic spaces for the speakers of these languages.

Keywords: Discipline-Specific Terminology; Indigenous Language; Language as a Resource; Terminology in isiZulu; Transliteration

1. Introduction

The Constitution of South Africa encompasses a bill of rights that recognises all human rights, including linguistic rights. Hence the multilingual status of the Republic of South Africa (RSA, henceforth, South Africa) is enshrined in its Constitution (Khumalo, 2016). The Constitution (Act 108 of 1996) originally recognises eleven languages as official languages of the country, with a recent addition of South African Sign language in 2023.¹ The eleven languages as tabled in the 1996 constitution are nine languages of indigenous descent—Sepedi, Sesotho, Setswana, Xitsonga, Tshivenda, siSwati, isiNdebele, isiXhosa, isiZulu—and two languages of foreign descent—English and Afrikaans (RSA 1996).

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The multilingualism as expounded in the Constitution is preceded by a history of official bilingualism in South Africa with English and Afrikaans as the two main languages in education prior to 1994 (Beukes, 2010). This bilingual policy relegated the indigenous languages to the background for limited use in ethnically segregated homelands designated for African ethnic communities of South Africa. In these homelands, the indigenous languages were used in primary school education and only on 'soft' subjects in accordance with the Bantu Education Act of 1953 (Martin, 1997; Prah, 2007). The English/Afrikaans bilingual policy of Bantu Education was enforced in secondary school education for all South African linguistic communities including indigenous communities. This policy ultimately sparked the well-known 1976 Soweto uprisings during which African students challenged the rule that English/Afrikaans should be, to equal parts, the only media of instruction in schools (Magocha et al., 2019). Even though African students of 1976 fought the domination of Afrikaans, their motive was not to promote the use of African indigenous languages at post-primary education level. The preference was to use English as the main medium of instruction. Thus, linguistic tendencies in South Africa have been inclined towards English for a long time; this pro-English attitude constitutes a consistent trend towards monolingualism in higher societal domains, particularly in education (Heugh, 2002) that persists today.

The preference for English emanates from negative attitudes that indigenous linguistic communities in South Africa hold towards Afrikaans on the one hand, and their own indigenous languages on the other hand. With regards to Afrikaans, the politically motivated mandatory use of Afrikaans as a medium of instruction for fifty percent of subjects in secondary schools, led to a strong resistance and aggravated existing negative attitudes towards the language. Afrikaans was seen as an instrument of oppression and dominance. In contrast, English was perceived as an international language that opened avenues of liberation for the oppressed masses (Prah, 2007). With regards to African indigenous languages, their traditional use in high status domains was disrupted by colonialism followed by Apartheid. This long-lasting demotion led to strong perceptions amongst indigenous linguistic communities that their languages are not equipped and/or viable for use in high-prestige societal domains such as education, politics, trade, law, and the arts (Webb, 2013). Such attitudes further paved the way for English as the language of choice, a vehicle for social mobility and access to economic goods (Heugh, 2002). As Posel and Zeller (2016, p. 360) argue, many communities in South Africa bestow high socio-economic value to English as a language of "upward social mobility." The systematic relegation of indigenous languages to the periphery of socio-economic and academic spaces led to a huge gap between these languages and colonial languages, particularly English (Nhongo, 2024). It is against this

background that the Constitution of South Africa in 1996 accorded an official status to nine indigenous African languages. Accordingly, the Constitution mandates for the equitable use of all official languages.

Since 1996, national, provincial and institutional legislation and policies have been promulgated as a response to the Constitutional directive. The University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN)'s response to the Constitutional directive has been to consistently promote the regionally widely spoken isiZulu as one of the official languages of the university in addition to English. In actualizing this drive, UKZN has, among other things, developed discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu (Khumalo, 2016). The development of this terminology is in line with one of the aims of the university's language policy which is to, "... become a national hub in the development of isiZulu national corpus and the development and standardization of isiZulu technical terminology and its dissemination" (UKZN, 2014, p. 4).

The current paper reviews literature on multilingualism in South Africa including the role of indigenous languages in education; thereafter we present the research design; we then discuss the data; present the findings; and make recommendations on the use of indigenous languages in education and finally draw conclusions from the presented research.

2. Background

In this section, firstly, we interrogate the role of language legislation and policies in entrenching multilingualism in South Africa. These are the enablers in promotion and use of indigenous languages in the South African education sector. Secondly, we interrogate research done on mitigating against monolingualism, including, the intellectualisation of African languages. Thirdly, we review previous research on the role of indigenous languages in education, particularly, higher education. Fourthly, we detail the development of discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu at the UKZN as an institutional response to the Constitutional directives as stated in chapter 1 subsection 6(2) of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (2011).

2.1. Language legislation and multilingualism in South Africa

Heugh (2002, p. 173) propagates for interweaving language policies and implementation plans as well as developing compatible goals between the two. In the case of South Africa, statutes and policies on language use need to be compatible for multilingualism to be realised in the education sector, and they all need to work in tandem as enablers of multilingualism. Multilingualism will be realised, Siziba (2024) argues, if the language policies spell out strategies for intellectualising African languages in their implementation plans.

Gradual steps have been taken at national, provincial, and institutional levels to realise multilingualism through elevating the status and use of all official languages. The Language-in-Education Policy aims at creating a non-racial nation while encouraging respect for each other's languages (RSA, 1997). The Language Policy for Higher Education (2002) acknowledges the need to develop the indigenous languages of South Africa as media of instruction in higher education contexts (RSA, 2002). The 2020 review of the 2002 policy foregrounds the promotion of multilingualism in all functional domains of the South African universities by staff and students to attain meaningful access and participation (RSA, 2020). The preamble to Chapter nine of the National Development Plan (2011, p. 261) declares, "we live the joy of speaking many languages." This declaration manifests the government's commitment to make multilingualism a reality in South Africa. The Use of Official Languages Act (2012) regulates and monitors the use of the South African official languages by the national departments, the national public entities, and the national public enterprises (RSA, 2012). The UKZN Language Policy and Plan (2014) declares the commitment by the university to develop isiZulu as a second medium of instruction and while also preserving English as the primary medium of instruction (UKZN, 2014). These steps guide the enactment of multilingualism with the focus on the indigenous languages of the country. Therefore, national and institutional language policies are part of a social justice and empowerment drive that creates access to knowledge in all societal spaces for the indigenous people of South Africa.

In its language policy, the UKZN committed to the development of discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu. Through its University Language Planning and Development Office (ULPDO), the university has developed discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu in twenty disciplines already, starting out in the early 2010s with disciplines like Administration, Anatomy, Architecture, Computer Science, Environmental Science, Law, Physics, Psychology, and Nursing (Khumalo, 2017). The UKZN—in line with the Constitutional directive—is determined to accelerate the process of intellectualizing isiZulu, i.e., one of South Africa's widely spoken languages countrywide and in the province of KwaZulu-Natal (Posel et al., 2020).

2.2. Mitigating monolingualism through the intellectualization of African languages

Based on the Constitutional directive of achieving parity of esteem and equitable use, the indigenous languages of South Africa need to be used in high domains such as in education from primary school to tertiary levels. Their extended use requires that these indigenous languages be intellectualized (Bamgbose, 2011). Intellectualizing a language involves capturing available knowledge in multiple retrievable forms—print, audio-visual, digital, web,

etc.—and subsequently using the language (Prah, 2017). An intellectualized language as one that can be used in educating a person in any field of knowledge from kindergarten up to tertiary level (Sibayan, 1999, as cited in Prah, 2017). For South African indigenous languages, this entails using the languages to disseminate knowledge in all subject areas including core fields like mathematics, science, technology, and commerce.

However, the paucity of terminology in indigenous languages is one of the obstacles that prevent stakeholders from considering the wider use of these languages. Thus, it is mandatory to develop of discipline-specific terminology in these languages (Prah, 2017). According to Alberts (2010), languages can develop into functional languages because once they have terminology, we can unlock innovative skills through these languages. The UKZN has stepped up to intellectualise isiZulu and continuously develops discipline-specific terminology with the aim of using isiZulu as an official language of the university. The development of terminologies in isiZulu by the UKZN reinforces the argument that university language policies are appropriately placed as enablers of intellectualising the indigenous African languages (Siziba, 2024).

To enhance the functionality of the indigenous languages and to capture innovative traits in languages, terminology development may need to consider a translanguaging approach as a viable option. Translanguaging, as used in this paper, refers to linguistic fluidity that characterises language practices for multilingual speakers (Makalela, 2015; see also Motaung, 2024; Nkhi & Shange, 2024; Xu & Fang, 2024). Rather than using separate, monolithic language systems, multilingual speakers may process and deploy linguistic information from one integrated and combined linguistic repertoire. Translanguaging mitigates against monolingualism as it captures the heterogeneity of language practices for multilingual speakers in meaning-making processes (Garcia et al., 2021). From a pedagogic perspective, translanguaging facilitates effective communication in multilingual classrooms (Nhongo & Tshotsho, 2020) and furthermore affords epistemic access to content knowledge for multilingual speakers (Chaka, 2024). In a study conducted by Chambara and Zano (2019) on school learners in a Chemistry classroom, in post-test experiments, the learners show mastery of subject content which is evidence for epistemological access to Chemistry—one of the ‘core’ subjects perceived to be challenging to the non-mother tongue speakers of English. Based on such results, Nhongo and Tshotsho (2020, p. 80) advocate for translanguaging as “the ideal tool for teaching Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) subjects in African languages.”

In terminology development, translanguaging may lead to transliterated terms. Transliterated terms exhibit features of both the source language (here English) and the target language (here isiZulu). Sager (1990, p. 90) defines

transliteration as “the taking over of the term from another language but adjusting its morphological characteristics, pronunciation and spelling.” Transliterated terms, hence, have a semblance with source language terms but share morphological and phonetical features of the target language. Examples in Table (1) illustrate the difference between transliterated terms and terms that are the outcome of formal translation and term development processes and that adhere solely to the rules of the target language.

Table 1
Transliteration Versus Formal Translation

Source term (English)	Transliteration	Target term (isiZulu)
Batten	ibhathini	ithandela
Hysteresis	ihisterisisi	ukusilela
Soleus	isoliyusi	umsipha wesihluzi

As Table 1 illustrates, transliteration may bridge the gap between source terms and target terms. We hypothesise that students may better understand, use, and retain academic source terms by activating all their linguistic resources simultaneously through transliteration.

2.3. The role of indigenous languages in higher education

As one central educational goal, Skutnabb-Kangas (2009, p. 38) mentions, “a fair chance of achieving academically at school.” This, she asserts, is possible through a multilingual education that empowers indigenous languages in education (*ibid*). Multilingual education, particularly the use of indigenous languages is a contested terrain in South Africa. As Magocha et al. (2019, p. 254) point out, “Students are unlikely to choose learning in their mother tongue when doing so does not offer any prospects of a good job or social progression.” Hence, many students hope for economic returns by studying through English. However, research shows that most students in South Africa have a very limited command of English; a fact that impacts negatively on their academic performance (Mlachila & Moeletsi, 2019). Poor academic performance, low throughput rates, and high dropout rates are largely attributed to the use of English as medium of instruction for non-mother tongue speakers (see, for instance, Mkhize & Balfour, 2017; Read & Du Plessis, 2021, Spaul, 2013). According to Heugh (2002), in a multilingual context, where the dominant language is a foreign language, linguistic development in the indigenous languages needs to be foregrounded. The second language—here English—must be added subsequently to the L1 to allow for the development of proficiency in both languages. The argument acknowledges that English cannot be abandoned (Siziba, 2024). However, English must be used alongside indigenous languages.

The use of an indigenous language in education upholds the notion of linguistic rights and acknowledges that one's language is an essential resource for the attainment of one's full potential (Mutasa, 2015). In this context, Mutasa (2015, p. 47) contends that a language "enables its people to function fully as members of the linguistic group into which they are born." The notion of language as a resource acknowledges the value of linguistic multiplicity. Multilingual speakers are at an advantage as they draw on several linguistic repertoires which are each "an enriching source of knowledge for their work and study" (Harrison, 2007, p. 83). Consequently, Siziba (2024, p. 203) considers language "as a resource for its capability to convey valuable knowledge in educational contexts."

The use of English as the main medium of instruction in South Africa restricts the speakers of indigenous languages in exercising their linguistic rights which furthermore limits them in accessing important resources for knowledge access, entrepreneurship and innovation. Nomlomo and Katiya's (2018) research indicates that South African students who had maximum exposure to their indigenous language benefit from the use of multilingual glossaries even in STEM subjects like electrical engineering. Learning is facilitated if the knowledge imparted resonates with students culturally and/or linguistically (Bethke, 2021). Speakers of indigenous languages thus draw from their linguistic repertoires a resource for self-development. The opportunity to use their languages simultaneously may unlock access to academic knowledge and might also mitigate cognitive overload that could otherwise impede their learning opportunities (Dukhan et al., 2016). The multilingual mind can be viewed as a unitary network through which speakers access meaning from all its languages (Garcia et al., 2021).

2.4. The development of discipline-specific terminology at the UKZN

Baumann and Graves (2010, p. 6) give a two-fold definition of 'academic vocabulary': One narrow definition where academic vocabulary is seen as domain-specific or content-specific vocabulary used in specific disciplines such as biology, geometry, etc., and a second broader definition where academic vocabulary is defined as general academic vocabulary—the broad all-purpose terms as used across different disciplines.

In this paper, the term 'discipline-specific terminology' is used to refer to academic vocabulary as denoted in the first definition. The development of terminology is a long, time-consuming, and labour-intensive process which requires specialized skills, commitment as well as intense consultation (Nhongo, 2024). UKZN embarked on a five-stage terminology development process: (1) harvesting the existing terms currently in use, (2) describing and translating the terms that have been harvested, (3) consulting and verifying the terms with the end-users, (4) authenticating and standardizing the terms

through the official national structures, and (5) listing the terms in the terminology databases for wider institutional and national usage (Khumalo, 2017). Although the ULPDO pioneers the process, the office works in collaboration with national language structures, namely, the Pan South African Language Board (PanSALB) and the isiZulu National Language Body (*Umkhandlu Wesizulu KaZwelonke—UMZUKAZWE*) (*ibid*).

The UKZN terminology development process involves terminology harvesting by discipline experts—lecturers—who are committed to realizing the English/isiZulu bilingual policy of the UKZN. They harvest terms from their course content (handouts, slides, exam papers) and/or books (Khumalo 2017). Once the terms are harvested, the ULPDO convenes an intense consultative workshop in which the discipline experts, lexicographers, linguists, terminologists, and students (the end-users) describe, create, and codify the isiZulu terms (*ibid*). The ULPDO draws panellists from lay people and from experts into a collaborative endeavour. The next stage in the process involves the authoritative bodies. The codified terms are verified in a consultative workshop wherein PanSALB consults further with academics and students. Upon satisfactory consultation, the terms are submitted to UMZUKAZWE for approval, authentication and standardization (Khumalo 2017). To conclude the entire process, once all the stakeholders agree, the ULPDO, through the university structures, disseminates the terms and stores them in open-access databases.

All currently available terminology is available on the university weblink² and on a mobile application the Zulu Lexicon which may be downloaded from Google Play Store. Only two disciplines—Architecture and Law—have published their terminology in isiZulu as book publications so far (Zungu, 2021). Through the terminology in their L1, isiZulu L1 speaking students have an additional resource which enables them to conceptualize discipline-specific terms better as they access these terms in both their L2 (English) and their L1 (isiZulu). The UKZN is thus expanding the functional space of African languages and is continuously dismantling the language barrier that was erected using predominantly English in South African higher education (Nkomo, 2019). Zungu (2021) echoes the sentiment as she argues that the discipline-specific terminology serves as a gateway to overcoming the language barrier—it ensures functional bilingualism as stipulated in the university language policy, and enhances opportunities for optimal academic performance for isiZulu L1 students.

In the light of the background given, the objectives of this paper are:

1. To determine the way in which isiZulu L1 students acknowledge discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu.

2. To explore the extent to which isiZulu L1 students find discipline-specific terminology resourceful in their academic endeavours.

The questions we seek to address in this paper are, therefore:

1. In which manner do isiZulu L1 students acknowledge discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu?
2. To what extent do isiZulu L1 students find the discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu resourceful in their academic endeavours?

3. Method

Our research design is interpretive in nature (cf. Kivunja & Kuyini, 2017) as we explore the interplay between discipline-specific terminology and isiZulu L1 students who are potential beneficiaries of this resource. The data used to respond to the research questions is sourced from focus group interviews.

Prior to conducting focus group interviews, we sought ethical clearance (i.e., Ethical Clearance number HSS/0755/018D) from the university Ethics and Research office. The participants ($N=28$) were selected purposefully to meet two criteria: (1) be mother-tongue speakers of isiZulu, and (2) be enrolled in a first-year module at UKZN in the eight disciplines targeted for this enquiry. These disciplines included four wherein the terminology in isiZulu had been developed (Architecture, Anatomy, Law, and Physics) and four disciplines wherein the terminology in isiZulu had not been developed (Community Development, Physiology, Management, and Chemistry) at the time of the investigation. Our participants signed informed consent forms in accordance with the Ethics guidelines of the university. Focus group interview transcripts were thematically analysed using *NVivo Pro* software.

Ten terms from four discipline lists (Anatomy, Architecture, Law and Physics) in isiZulu—see Appendix A at the end of the paper—were used to probe the students' acknowledgement of the terminology and their perception of the resourcefulness of this terminology.

4. Results

The participants expressed their attitudes towards the availability of discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu at the UKZN. The sourced data responds to the two questions that underlay this investigation: Firstly, in which manner do isiZulu L1 students acknowledge discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu? Secondly, to what extent do isiZulu L1 students find the discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu resourceful in their academic endeavours?

4.1. Acknowledgement of discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu

Overall, we found that isiZulu L1 students welcome the availability of discipline-specific terminologies in isiZulu, a language that they are more proficient in than in their second language, English. One participant verifies this observation as seen in example (1).

- (1) MNGT4: However, since isiZulu is our Home Language, it may make things easier for us to understand certain concepts.

The claim made by MNGT4 indicates a strong allegiance to isiZulu. For this participant, isiZulu enables learning, it places him at ease with the discipline concepts, and it affords him the comprehensibility of the discipline concepts. An exclusive use of English would disadvantage this student and many others who are in the same position.

As a language offered at home language level at school, isiZulu is frequently used across different subjects during basic and secondary education. In example (2), one participant testifies that a substantial number of students have developed a preference for isiZulu because of such experiences during their schooling career.

- (2) LAWS2: Particularly those who did isiZulu as a Home Language throughout their school years may prefer to access information in isiZulu. It would be beneficial for them to have a resource in isiZulu.

To concur, another participant—see example (3)—supports the idea that content presented in isiZulu might lead to a deeper understanding.

- (3) LAWS9: It would help. The truth is that for some of us students, we understand content clearly if it is presented/explained in isiZulu our HL.

Indicating that the use of isiZulu would benefit ‘some’ students—but maybe not all students—is evidence that language learning experiences vary across students of African descent. Consequently, participants who were enrolled for isiZulu HL at basic/secondary education levels recognize discipline-specific terminology lists in their Home Language as a valuable resource. Through acknowledging the availability and the usefulness of discipline-specific terminologies in isiZulu, the participants favour the advancement of isiZulu.

These participants support the more widespread promotion of isiZulu in academic contexts. Yet, most of our participants do not find it easy to bridge the gap from English terminology to formally translated isiZulu terminology.

Hence, they provide strong arguments in favour of transliterated terms. One participant expresses their own experience with this process in example (4).

- (4) ACTT1: Terminology in 'proper' isiZulu is also challenging on its own; sometimes you do not recognise what is referred to, but you can recognise the term in the transliterated term from English.

This participant acknowledges and welcomes the use of isiZulu. The articulation, "Terminology in 'proper' isiZulu is also challenging . . .," indicates that even though the participant identifies as isiZulu L1 speaker, proficiency in isiZulu may be insufficient to decipher formal terminology in the language. However, it is not only for this reason that our participants welcome transliterated terms, see example (5) for another argument in favour of transliterated terms.

- (5) ANAT5: Another instance is where we misspell words; to have terms that are loanwords will assist to remember the correct spelling—'fascia' may be translated as '*fashiya*'—exactly how you pronounce it. English spelling is at times complicated.

For participant ANAT5, transliteration assists in recalling the spelling of the term in English. In addition, allowing for transliterated terms accommodates the differing language learning experiences in isiZulu in as much as it does accommodate a range of experiences in English. This is evident in the claim that one participant makes in example (6).

- (6) CODE9: The use of transliterated terms would be much preferable since it will be at a level that we use on daily basis.

Example (6) reflects the daily reality of our participants who study at an urban university with over 40 000 national and international students who speak a multitude of different languages. Translanguaging between various languages is more common than using one single language register. Transliterated terminology fits into this common language practice.

4.2. The resourcefulness of discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu

On the question to which extent isiZulu L1 students find the discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu resourceful in their academic endeavours, our data show three different ways in which the students find the terminology resourceful: for the facilitation of understanding, for the deconstruction of discipline-specific concepts, and for the enhanced recall of concepts during assessments.

According to participant PHYS16, the terminologies in isiZulu facilitate the understanding of discipline-specific concepts, see example (7).

- (7) PHYS16: Terms would be far easier to grasp if they were taught in isiZulu. The issue of not learning using your home language is that it becomes ten times harder as you first must understand what is said and then try to simplify it into your own language and this is discouraging and tedious.

In this testimony, the participant points out how discipline-specific concepts often appear inaccessible and incomprehensible. However, this problem may be mitigated by use of a familiar language. According to this participant, the L1 can be an enabler but the student also feels that access to relevant information in their L1 is not always available. Therefore, students are forced to individually embark on searches for the meanings of concepts and for translation equivalents in their first languages. This process is perceived as discouraging and tedious. Participant LAWS2 supports this assertion in example (8).

- (8) LAWS2: We get about ten unfamiliar terms daily. So, if there is no translation at all or terminologies in isiZulu that would mean doing extra research all the time in trying to understand each new term and that will take time. If the terms are available in isiZulu as well, that would make things easier for the L1 speaking students.

In both examples (7) and (8), the issue of time constraints and the burden of extra work that comes with studying in a foreign language are very prominent. These aspects are also noticeable in example (9). Participant CODE9 highlights how second language speakers might be perceived as not putting enough effort into their studies. The participant perceives the fact that university content is mostly presented in English as disadvantaging speakers of indigenous languages like isiZulu. This is evidenced in the phrase "... the effort may not be good enough." The participant is clearly frustrated because the isiZulu speaking students are unable to unpack the meanings of all English terms and translate them into isiZulu because of the enormous workload that all students at a tertiary institution are facing anyway.

- (9) CODE9: Making an example of "global financial institutions" he said that one has to first understand what this term means. When he asked us if we know what it means, no one answered. He then explained to us in isiZulu what it means and what it entails, then we understood. What I am trying to say is that we do try to put effort into our work; but the

effort may not be good enough. This is because of limited time—we cannot afford to disintegrate every term that challenges us in English with the huge loads of work that we have in all the modules that we are registered for.

Participant LAWS2 and CODE9 concur that term lists in isiZulu save L1 students time when they study. They provide a resource in an accessible language that facilitates an understanding of the numerous academic concepts that the students encounter daily. For these participants, time for studying will be optimised through easily accessible term lists. Participant ANAT3 reinforces this assertion in example (10).

- (10) ANAT3: A project such as this one (*discipline-specific terms in isiZulu—our addition*) might assist when one does self-study afterwards. We would have a resource to refer to in trying to understand the concepts we struggle with. We may use this together with the lecture notes/textbooks in English.

In example (10), the participant highlights the usefulness of term lists that may alleviate the daily struggle that is experienced when the language used to present the academic content, and which denotes discipline-specific concepts, is inaccessible.

Over and above facilitating understanding, the participants appreciate the resourcefulness of the terms in isiZulu in deconstructing the discipline-specific concepts. Participant PHYS12 attests to this in example (11).

- (11) PHYS12: I remember once when we were writing Physics, one question worth seven (7) marks asked about 'a hovering helicopter'; we all got zero (0) because we did not understand what 'hovering' meant. Our teacher explained in isiZulu afterwards that hovering meant that the helicopter was not moving thus the velocity was at zero. We were all devastated because that would have been an easy question.

For PHYS12 deconstructing concepts denoted through isiZulu terms assists in comprehending the concepts faster. When such a deconstruction is non-existent, students are placed at a clear disadvantage (see example (11)).

The resourcefulness of the terms in isiZulu extends to enabling recall of concepts during assessments. When the students are enabled to access academic terms in isiZulu, to deconstruct their meaning and to thus arrive at a clear understanding of the underlying concepts, they will also be empowered

to recall relevant terms during assessments more easily. See example (12) where participant PHLG1 describes such a case.

- (12) PHLG1: In Anatomy, for example, you read a term, and you are clueless as to what it means. This makes it even difficult to recall the term during assessments. However, if the term is also available in isiZulu, then I would recall it faster.

In example (12), participant PHLG1 indicates that there is a higher rate of retention of the concepts if students access them through isiZulu as well compared to when concepts are accessed through English only. Another participant, CHEM2, concurs with this experience as shown in example (13).

- (13) CHEM2: For me when I am in class it does happen that I do not understand an explanation given in English but when I get an explanation in isiZulu, I get an understanding; and I realise that it is a familiar term. So, it is better to jot the isiZulu version down to refer to it later and you can recall the English term because that is the language we are using.

According to these participants, even in a situation where English remains the primary medium of instruction and assessment, the availability of additional discipline-specific terms in isiZulu facilitates both the understanding, the retention and hence the recall of concepts.

5. Discussion

The current research is based on the voices of L1 isiZulu speaking at a tertiary institution in South Africa where the dominant language of teaching and learning is English. Our participants—whose perceptions are captured in examples (1) to (13)—acknowledge the availability of discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu and express why they appreciate the resourcefulness of available discipline specific term lists in isiZulu.

Throughout the testimonies of our participants it transpires that their levels of proficiency in English vary which in turn influences their ability to decipher formal academic terms in their L2 (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018, 2020, 2023a). Like most African students who do not speak English as a first language, they struggle in the South African education system. This is because “[a]lthough the importance of English is recognised by the authorities, very few effective provisions are made to teach English to the required levels of proficiency” (Magocha et al., 2019, p. 257). Therefore, not all students reach academic language proficiency in English.

This devastating assessment rests on the fact that in South Africa, language offerings are not uniform at basic education level. As per the Language-in-Education Policy (1997), a learner may learn language subjects either at Home Language (HL) level, First Additional Language Level (FAL), or Second Additional Language Level (SAL)—a different level for each language subject undertaken. The offering of an African Language at Home Language level entails that English must be taken as First Additional Language. This means that even though English is the dominant medium of instruction (MoI) throughout the education system, the learning experiences of students with an African L1 are more oriented towards their African Home Language than towards English. In addition, “non-mother tongue speakers of English have diminished exposure to the primary MoI, English” (Magocha et al., 2019, p. 257) outside the schooling system. Consequently, many students have a low proficiency level in English and much higher proficiency levels in isiZulu because they studied their home language (L1) at home language level at basic education (from primary school years to secondary school years—grade 0 to grade 12). Additionally, for these students isiZulu is their dominant language that they constantly use across different domains (Zungu, 2021).

Since isiZulu is a language they most frequently use, L1 students tend to appreciate the presence of discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu. The use of isiZulu helps them to better understand academic content. This enhanced understanding seems to be coupled with sustainable knowledge creation. In L1 isiZulu speaking students, who have access to isiZulu terms, the self-reported retention rate of a discipline’s episteme is higher; an advantage that they tap into both while they study and while they are being assessed. In these respects, our students report overall similar experiences as the participants in Chambara and Zano’s (2019) study which took place in a chemistry classroom. In both cases, the accessibility of discipline specific concepts through the first language provides a ‘gateway’ to academic meaning making that does not seem to be available through the second language—i.e., English. Hence, students who have access to terminology in their L1 understand discipline content better (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016); their linguistic repertoires in the L1 and the L2 mediate understanding and mutually enhance each other (Chambara & Zano, 2019). Our participants report that this advantage aids them both while they are attending in classes, and while they are studying on their own: The isiZulu terms in conjunction with the English terms consistently enable them to unlock discipline-specific conceptual content. This kind of double de-coding facilitates deeper learning of the subject content (Bethke, 2021). A similar point is made by Garcia et al (2021) who state that the simultaneous employment of all the languages in the minds of multilingual students may enable students to “make meaning by drawing from complex, interrelated linguistic-semiotic and multimodal repertoires” (p. 221).

Participants in the current study highlight the importance of transliterated terms in this process of mediating between academic terms in their L2 (English) and formal terms in their L1 (isiZulu). In their experience, transliterated terms can enhance the above-mentioned advantages of having bilingual terminology available. Since transliterated terms are not guided by conventional rules, users may even coin their own terms in a convenient manner that is akin to the original (English) pronunciation of the source term. Hence, our participants support sentiments shared by Nhongo (2024) who discusses advantages of transliterated terms that exemplify a less purist and less prescriptive approach to terminology creation (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2022). The transliteration of terms may even be conceptualised as an essentially transformational approach to terminology development as it mirrors the multilingual context of South Africa and the above-mentioned heterogeneity of language proficiencies across learners at all levels of the education system. This assessment is in line with Nhongo and Tshotsho (2020) who also find that transliterated terms “exert less cognitive burden on language users who are coming from diverse linguistic backgrounds” (p. 83). Transliterated terms may thus play a pivotal role in unlocking access to discipline specific epistemes.

One advantage of transliterated isiZulu terms that our participants mention is that these terms seem to enable them to decipher the morphology of discipline-specific terms in English. This in turn allows them to recognize discipline-specific terms more easily and at a faster pace. Transliterated terms make it more effortless to establish a connection with the English source term. The subtlety between the English term and the transliterated isiZulu term seems to make it simpler for the students to learn the correct spelling conventions in English. All these aspects taken together lead to a more straightforward access to the denoted academic concept.

The participants also report that they retain terms and their meaning in memory with greater ease when transliterated terms are available. Better retention seems to ultimately result in faster recall. Increased recognition, understanding, retention and recall of terms and the concepts that they denote places emphasis on the cognitive, communicative and linguistic dimensions that a particular language may serve in facilitating understanding (Nhongo 2024). In line with these observations, the current study finds that given a choice, our participants have strong arguments for the inclusion of isiZulu transliterated terms over and above the available terms in English and in formal isiZulu.

In sum, the participants in our investigation welcome the respective discipline-specific terminology list in isiZulu as a valuable resource. The terminology list saves them precious time when they study as it leads to an easier and longer

retainment of discipline concepts. This, in turn, enhances performance during assessments. Our findings affirm that isiZulu L1 students acknowledge the discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu across the disciplines covered in this investigation. In addition, our participants find the terms in isiZulu resourceful, even more so they advocate for transliterated terms in addition to formal translations. As Nhongo (2024) argues, transliterated terms allow users to shuttle between two languages thus enhancing an understanding of the discipline-specific concept.

Based on these findings, we argue that the wider use of African languages in tertiary education would cater for the differing language learning experiences that exist across L1 speakers of African Languages in South Africa—particularly for L1 speakers who have learnt English as FAL or as SAL. Such a practical implementation of the constitutional mandate would ensure linguistic human rights for the majority of South Africans students.

6. Conclusion

The Constitution of South Africa, the subsequent language statutes and policies all paved the way to redress the linguistic injustices of the past. In addition to statutes and policies, implementation plans need to be actioned at all levels—governmental, provincial, and institutional. The ULPDO at the UKZN has taken strides to put policy into practice by continuously developing discipline-specific terminology in isiZulu; to date such terminology lists exist for twenty disciplines. This effort is significant in two ways. On the one hand, successful terminology development is a manifestation of the potential that indigenous languages possess to evolve as academic languages. This development may not be an overnight process, and it may require extensive financial and human resources to materialize; but it is a step in the right direction. On the other hand, terminology development reduces the paucity of discipline-specific vocabulary. The argument that indigenous languages lack discipline specific terminology has consistently inhibited the use of the indigenous languages in education and other sectors. Developing discipline-specific terminologies in isiZulu at UKZN is one of the blocks in the process of intellectualising isiZulu (Zungu, 2021). When speakers of indigenous languages access knowledge through their L1, they are empowered. Acquisition, recognition, retention, and recall of knowledge content is accelerated when learning happens in the L1 as compared to learning through the L2, English. Access to knowledge in a familiar language may be an enabler for the speakers of indigenous languages, it may enhance their success rates throughout the education system and thereby increase their access to the job market and much sought-after economic returns. With the availability and continuous use of the resources in indigenous languages, speakers of these languages may develop confidence towards their languages and may unlock their full potentials.

The strides taken by the UKZN represent some of many possible avenues that have the potential to elevate the status of the indigenous languages of South Africa; not just in paper—i.e., in statutes and policies—but in practice. Universities, as research institutions are well positioned to realize the Constitutional mandate as tabled in chapter one, subsection six. The existence of discipline-specific terminology in indigenous languages not only breaks the ‘hegemony’ of English monolingualism in the education sector but also offers the speakers of indigenous languages a panacea to the inaccessibility of academic spaces.

Notes

1. For more on this, see Balosa (2024) and Mapuya (2024).
2. <https://ukzntermbank.ukzn.ac.za/PublicSearch.aspx>

Authors’ Statement

Muhle MaShezi Sibisi contributed to sections 1, 2, 3 & 4, and Heike Tappe worked on sections 4, 5 & 6.

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Appendix A: Lists of Terms in isiZulu Extracted from UKZN Term Bank and the Zulu Lexicon Mobile Application

College of Humanities:

Architecture

udaka lobumba

Umhlobisansika
 Igumbimkhathi
 Isithungo
 Isikhocosendlu
 ithandela/ibhathini
 Umshayo
 Isibopho
 isigqokwana sensika yokubambelela
 udonga olumahhadla

College of Agriculture and Engineering Sciences: Physics

Umsebe
 thathela kungqangqazela
 zungeza/zongoloza/jikeleza
 umsindo ongazwakali/umsindobuthule
 ubungangomdlandla
 Ukusilela
 okucacile/okusobala
 Iyengelamcijo
 isifundomkhathi/isayensi
 yomlandomkhathi
 okubonwa yiso

College of Health Sciences:

Anatomy

okuphathelene nokukhiqizwa
 kwamafutha
 imizwa ezungelezile
 izicutshana/ izinhlayiya ezihlangene
 umsipha wesihluzi
 isikhiqizambewu
 okusaphonjwana
 Umlomo
 okuphathelene nenqulu/okwenqulu
 Uvulavale
 iphakathi nendawo

College of Law and Management Sciences: Law

isimangalo sesinxephezelo
 [-]thobelile
 inhlango yabammeli basemajajini
 umyalezo wommeli wasemajajini
 ubelelesi obuthinta amazwe ngamazwe
 isenzo ngokweso lomthetho
 Impikiswano
 [-]dalula/[-]veza
 umthetho ongabhaliwe

amacala ahlanganisiwe/ ingxubemacala

Appendix B: Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
DBE	Department of Basic Education (Republic of South Africa)
MoI	Medium of Instruction
PanSALB	Pan South African Language Board
RSA	Republic of South Africa
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
ULPDO	University Language Planning and Development Office
UMZUKAZWE	Umkhandlu wesiZulu kaZwelonke (National isiZulu Language Board)
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
UKZN	University of KwaZulu-Natal
